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**Neuromarketing indicators of the perception of terroir stories in social media
video content**

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Abstract. The article examines the concept of terroir as an element of marketing communications and its role in shaping brand authenticity. It is substantiated that the combination of terroir storytelling and video marketing on social media fosters an emotional connection between the brand and the consumer, thereby strengthening trust, loyalty, and a positive perception of products associated with a specific territory. The **purpose of the study** is to summarize scientific approaches to the analysis of terroir in marketing communications and to systematize neuromarketing indicators for assessing the perception of terroir video stories on social media. The **methodological basis** of the research is an interdisciplinary approach that combines the analysis of modern theories of storytelling, brand authenticity, and neuromarketing methods. Content analysis of scientific sources and the method of systematization were used to generalize approaches to measuring emotional engagement and audience reactions to video content. The article presents a description of key neuromarketing indicators for analyzing video materials with terroir-related narratives. The proposed formulas for calculating indicators enable quantitative measurement of consumers' emotional and

cognitive reactions and comparison of the effectiveness of different video strategies. The **research results** demonstrated that the effectiveness of video storytelling increases when authentic visual images, realistic emotions, and natural environmental elements are combined. Video content that reflects nature, traditions, people, and production processes activates positive emotional responses, enhances brand trust, and creates a sense of belonging to the place of product origin. The application of neuromarketing indicators in the study of such content ensures a scientifically grounded assessment of emotional engagement and viewers' perception of terroir stories. **Conclusions.** The use of neuromarketing indicators enables more accurate evaluation of video storytelling effectiveness, optimization of brand communication strategies, and stronger positioning in the digital environment. The obtained results can be used for further research in the fields of neuromarketing, place branding, and emotional content marketing.

Keywords: place branding, storytelling, brand trust, emotional engagement, brand authenticity, video marketing.

Нейромаркетингові індикатори сприйняття історій про теруар у відеоконтенті соціальних мереж

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Анотація. У статті розглянуто концепт теруару як елемента маркетингових комунікацій та його роль у формуванні автентичності бренду. Обґрунтовано, що поєднання теруарного сторітелінгу та відеомаркетингу у соціальних мережах сприяє створенню емоційного зв'язку між брендом і споживачем, підсилюючи довіру, лояльність та позитивне сприйняття продукції, пов'язаної з певною територією. **Метою дослідження є**

узагальнення наукових підходів до аналізу теруару в маркетингових комунікаціях і систематизація нейромаркетингових індикаторів, що дозволяють оцінювати сприйняття відеоісторій про теруар у соціальних мережах. **Методологічною основою** дослідження є міждисциплінарний підхід, який поєднує аналіз сучасних теорій сторітелінгу, автентичності бренду та нейромаркетингових методів. Використано контент-аналіз наукових джерел і метод систематизації для узагальнення підходів до вимірювання емоційного залучення та реакцій аудиторії на відеоконтент. У статті представлено опис ключових нейромаркетингових показників, які можуть застосовуватися для аналізу відеоматеріалів із теруарними сюжетами. Запропоновані формули розрахунку індикаторів дозволяють кількісно вимірювати емоційні та когнітивні реакції споживачів і порівнювати ефективність різних відеостратегій. **Результати** дослідження засвідчили, що ефективність відеосторітелінгу зростає за умови поєднання автентичних візуальних образів, реалістичних емоцій та природних елементів середовища. Відеоконтент, який відображає природу, традиції, людей і процес виробництва, активує позитивні емоційні реакції, підвищує довіру до бренду й формує відчуття приналежності до місця походження продукту. Застосування нейромаркетингових індикаторів у дослідженнях такого контенту забезпечує науково обґрунтоване оцінювання емоційного залучення та сприйняття глядачами теруарних історій. **Висновки.** Використання нейромаркетингових індикаторів дає змогу підвищити точність оцінювання ефективності відеосторітелінгу, оптимізувати комунікаційні стратегії брендів і зміцнити їх позиціонування у цифровому середовищі. Отримані результати можуть бути використані для подальших досліджень у сфері нейромаркетингу, брендингу територій та емоційного контент-маркетингу.

Ключові слова: територіальний брендинг, сторітелінг, довіра до бренду, емоційне залучення, автентичність бренду, відеомаркетинг.

Statement of the problem. In the context of rapid technological development, video marketing is one of the most sought-after tools in marketing communications strategies. Brands actively use short videos on social networks to engage audiences, foster a sense of belonging, and build emotional connections. All this has a positive effect on consumer loyalty and brand recognition. The typical viewer interacts with the video, reacts to its aesthetic shots, and intensely perceives the sincerity and uniqueness of the story the company tells.

With this in mind, today's companies are increasingly interested in storytelling approaches in digital marketing that convey a brand's story through a unique culture, people, place and tradition. Particularly fascinating are terroir stories that emphasize the authenticity of the product through its origin, the natural conditions of production, the skill of the producers, or the architectural and cultural aspects. Brands widely use these concepts in marketing communications because video content based on terroir vividly reflects the area's uniqueness and creates an image of trust and product quality. Such stories emphasize the company's social responsibility and transparency, meeting modern social expectations for sustainable production.

As storytelling spreads, brands are integrating neuromarketing into their communication strategies. The study of consumer behavior while watching videos that contain stories about terroir, using modern innovative technologies and tools, as well as specific indicators, makes it possible to reliably and objectively determine the depth of emotional perception of the content, the level of attention, involvement and trust of viewers in specific plots or elements of the video. Neuromarketing indicators help determine exactly how terroir stories form an emotional connection between a brand and an audience.

Analysis of recent research and publications. A review of the literature on the researched topic shows a growing interest in the problems of brand authenticity, storytelling in communications and the use of neuromarketing methods to study emotional reactions of consumers to video content. Three key areas that form the

theoretical and methodological basis of this research can be traced in scientific literature.

M. Levchenko examines modern marketing strategies and advertising tools aimed at promoting business in emerging markets [1]. M. Marshchivskyy considers the marketing potential of sports federations as business platforms in the field of retail trade [2]. S. Khara investigates the application of artificial intelligence and deep learning technologies in the creation of photo and video content for the wedding industry [3].

In scientific works, the issue of terroir is investigated by various authors, in particular S. J. Charters, who defines terroir as a combination of natural, cultural and human factors that shape the authenticity of a product [4]. M. B. Beverland and co-authors consider terroir as a means of increasing trust in the brand through the communication of values and origin, emphasizing its symbolic importance in creating brand narratives [5]. I. G. Guerrero and co-authors analyze the role of terroir in consumer perceptions of product quality and the authenticity of the experience [6]. However, these studies mainly consider terroir in the context of traditional branding and consumer behavior, without paying sufficient attention to digital communications, particularly video storytelling on social networks and neo-marketing approaches.

The influence of storytelling on the formation of a positive attitude towards the brand in the digital environment is investigated by J. E. Escalas [7] and K. Fog, C. Budtz, P. Munch, and S. Blanchette [8], who emphasize the role of emotional narratives in creating trust and engaging consumers. The research articles of M. De Veirman, V. Cauberghe, L. Hudders [9], D. Apasrawirote, K. Yawised, M. Chatrangsan, P. Muneesawang [10], E. Ferrara, Z. Yang [11] focus on emotional sincerity and authenticity of content as key determinants of video marketing effectiveness. At the same time, most of these studies analyze communication effects at the behavioral level, without accounting for the neurophysiological aspects of emotional involvement. Therefore, there remains a need for complex approaches

that combine storytelling with neuromarketing methods for measuring audience reactions. A study by H. Plassmann, V. Venkatraman, S. A. Huettel, and C. Yoon examines neuromarketing methods for evaluating consumer reactions to content, in particular functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), electroencephalography (EEG), and eye tracking [12]. The authors show that the use of neurophysiological indicators enables more accurate assessment of emotional involvement, recall, and trust in a brand.

T. Z. Ramsøy offers a systematic approach to measuring consumers' emotional and cognitive responses in digital environments. The author describes in detail the methods of data collection and interpretation, such as EEG, galvanic skin response, and facial expression analysis, in marketing research [13]. This approach is essential for developing applied indicators of emotional perception of content. The study of M. Balconi and co-authors lays a methodological basis for analyzing the perception of video content at the level of subconscious reactions [14].

A group of authors led by G. Cartocci investigates neurophysiological reactions to video advertising in social networks. In their works, they demonstrate how biometric indicators reflect the level of attention, emotional arousal and positive attitude towards the brand [15]. The authors concluded that combining several methods increases the accuracy of measuring emotional impact. This study confirms the practical value of neuromarketing approaches for evaluating the perception of video content.

W. M. Lim offers a systemic road map for the development of neuromarketing research with the integration of EEG, artificial intelligence and big data (Big Data) [16]. The combination of neurophysiological measurements with machine learning algorithms enables deeper analysis of consumers' emotional reactions and predicts the effectiveness of marketing campaigns. This approach forms the basis for developing accurate and reliable indicators of emotional engagement in the digital environment.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. Despite the active development of scientific research on brand authenticity, storytelling, and neuromarketing methods for evaluating emotional reactions, several unresolved issues remain regarding the integration of these areas within digital video communications. Most modern works focus on studying the emotional impact of commercial advertising or traditional video marketing. However, existing scientific literature does not account for the specificity of terroir, which combines cultural, social, and natural factors in brand formation.

Comprehensive methods for quantifying viewers' authenticity and emotional involvement while watching video stories about terroir remain underdeveloped. Existing neuromarketing indicators do not fully account for the cognitive component of perception, which determines the depth of emotional immersion, brand trust, and content memorability.

Thus, the scientific problem is the lack of an integrated approach that combines terroir storytelling and neuromarketing measurements of emotional and cognitive reactions of consumers in social networks. It complicates the construction of a system of reliable indicators of emotional involvement and prevents quantitative analysis of the effectiveness of video content that reflects the brand's cultural identity and origin.

Formulation of the goals of the article (statement of the task). The purpose of the article is to generalize scientific approaches to the analysis of terroir in marketing communications and storytelling in video content, and to systematize the leading neuromarketing indicators for evaluating audience perception of terroir stories in video content on social networks.

Presentation of the primary research material. Modern scientific research on digital communication and storytelling focuses on the neuromarketing mechanisms that attract consumers during interaction with visual content that combines informational and aesthetic components.

As a result of the digital transformation in marketing strategies, there is a tendency to integrate traditional communication channels with digital platforms to expand audience reach and enhance the effectiveness of product promotion [1]. Mechanisms of brand commercialization based on partnerships, media activities, and sponsorship projects primarily rely on emotional perception, which allows strengthening brand recognition and target audience involvement [2, p. 40].

The success of such campaigns is based not only on the potential to expand the audience, but also on the use of neuromarketing approaches to build consumer loyalty. In this way, companies aim to deepen their understanding of consumer behavior, enabling them to adapt content to the social and cultural characteristics of target segments. In this context, special attention is paid to the roles of authenticity and terroir in building trust in the brand and strengthening its identity in the digital environment. And video marketing is a key tool for shaping the brand's emotional impact on consumers, combining emotional storytelling with authentic content that reflects the product's unique origin. Thus, the terroir approach becomes an essential component of the communication strategy, as it integrates elements of video marketing, cultural identity and brand values.

Terroir is a multidisciplinary concept that combines geography, agronomy, economics, sociology, and marketing. The term «terroir» (from the French «terroir») comes from the wine industry and refers to a set of natural-geographical, climatic, biological, historical-cultural, and social factors that shape the product's unique properties and affect its perception by consumers. S. Charters defines terroir as the interaction of natural, biological, and human factors (soil, climate, topography, variety, and skill of producers), which gives the product unique sensory characteristics [4].

Over time, the concept of terroir went beyond agrarian interpretation. It acquired the meaning of a multidimensional socio-cultural and marketing phenomenon. Today, terroir is considered not only a natural-geographical or economic factor, but also a strategic resource for brand positioning, combining

material (climate, soil, relief) and immaterial (traditions, cultural heritage, producers' skills) components. Thanks to this, terroir is actively used in the branding of territories and products with a pronounced place of origin, in particular coffee, cheese, wine, olive oil, «home-made» drinks, etc. [5, p. 587–588].

In modern marketing communications, terroir serves as the basis for brand authenticity, reflecting a region's uniqueness, history, and cultural features. Storytelling conveys the atmosphere of the area, production traditions, and the brand's value system, creating an emotional connection with the brand in consumers [4; 5; 6]. Video content that consistently demonstrates the history of production, local practices, and objects of cultural heritage increases brand recognition and audience engagement [6, p. 229].

Storytelling in brand communications is closely related to the psychological mechanism of consumer identification with the story's heroes. A positive attitude towards the brand is formed through immersion in the plot, which causes empathy and emotional empathy [7, p. 170]. Identification with characters builds trust and loyalty, while a consistent narrative structure ensures lasting memory. The classic concept of brand storytelling involves using key elements (hero, conflict, values, and emotional ending) to enhance recognition and create a clear brand identity [8]. Thus, storytelling becomes not only an artistic medium but also a technology of emotional influence.

The authenticity of the content determines the effectiveness of communication. Video storytelling with realistic emotions and natural character behavior activates neuromarketing responses, such as increased attention, emotional involvement, and trust [9, p. 801]. Empirical studies confirm that users respond better to real than staged stories, and short videos on TikTok and Instagram demonstrate the highest level of emotional interaction due to their dynamism and emotional saturation [10, p. 230]. The effectiveness of such formats is explained by the balance among duration, emotional intensity, and influence on user behavior. At the same time, the phenomenon of «emotional contagion», when the emotions of the

characters are transmitted to the audience, increases the willingness to share content that causes positive experiences [11].

In terroir stories, these mechanisms work particularly effectively. Short videos built on authentic elements of local culture, traditions, and natural landscapes create the effect of presence. Videos that incorporate elements of the region's cultural identity significantly increase audience emotional involvement and loyalty [9]. Terroir is also seen as part of the marketing concept of place, within which provenance is used to broadcast values, sustainability and craftsmanship in social media [4]. Video content created in a real production environment evokes a positive emotional response from viewers and forms lasting brand associations with a particular territory.

The use of terroir in video storytelling opens new opportunities for brand development in countries with significant cultural and natural potential, particularly in Ukraine. The video, which demonstrates the region's locality, traditions, and people, forms the brand's sensory identity, affecting the cognitive and emotional regions of viewers' brains [12, p. 570]. Neuromarketing research shows that videos with authentic origin stories activate mirror neurons, which are responsible for empathy and behavioral imitation [13], creating a «sense of place» effect.

Therefore, terroir can be defined as a narrative tool for forming an emotional connection between the brand and the consumer through an authentic representation of the place of origin. Video content built on terroir narratives becomes not only a means of communication but also a tool for neuro-emotional influence, strengthening trust and loyalty in the digital environment. In neuromarketing, terroir serves as an emotional stimulus that activates cognitive and physiological responses, as measured by specialized indicators. For the quantitative analysis of such reactions, modern studies use a set of neuromarketing methods that enable them to record exactly how the elements of the video elicit an emotional response and attract the audience. It enables a more objective, scientific evaluation of perceptions of video content.

In marketing research, neurophysiological methods not only allow evaluation of audience reactions but also provide a deeper understanding of the mechanisms underlying the perception of video materials. Neuromarketing indicators, particularly indicators of brain activity and micro-movements of the eyes, capture attention, cognitive tension, and emotional involvement while watching content. It allows you to determine how effectively the brand story holds the viewer's interest and inspires trust. In combination with content analysis, it enables quantitative assessment of which elements of the video (colors, sounds, faces, landscapes) elicit the strongest emotional reactions from consumers [12]. Applying these techniques to terroir video research allows us to empirically identify the «peak» moments of emotional engagement when the viewer experiences the highest levels of trust, joy, or inspiration.

Thus, combining analyses of behavioral and physiological reactions helps assess the depth of connection between the viewer and the brand, identify the most effective visual elements, and predict the audience's behavioral response.

Next, the method of calculating the leading neuromarketing indicators used in the analysis of video stories about terroir is presented. They include:

1. Degree of emotional engagement (Emotional Engagement Index). This indicator determines how strongly the viewer emotionally reacts to the video. It is measured using EEG or changes in facial expressions. For example, videos about natural landscapes, harvesting, or the work of artisans are usually approved and associated with industriousness. This consumer reaction leads to positive associations with the brand and loyalty.

The preliminary EEG indicator shows the general level of emotional response of the viewer while watching the video without normalization, that is, in a "raw", laboratory form. The indicator is calculated as the average ratio β/α for S segments of the video clip:

$$EEI_{raw} = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{s=1}^S \times \left(\frac{\beta}{\alpha} \right) ,$$

where EEI_{raw} is the previous («raw») of emotional involvement index (EEI); S is the number of segments of the video into which the recording is divided for analysis (for example, every 10 seconds or thematic scenes); β/α is the ratio between the amplitudes of β - and α -waves of the electroencephalogram recorded during viewing. In the formula, the β -rhythm (13–30 Hz) reflects an active cognitive state, attention, and emotional arousal; the α -rhythm (8–13 Hz) characterizes calmness, relaxation, and a slowing of the reaction. Therefore, the higher the β/α ratio, the greater the viewer's emotional activity and involvement.

Normalization to a scale of 0–1 (min–max) is calculated by the formula::

$$EEI_{raw} = \frac{EEI_{raw} - EEI_{min}}{EEI_{max} - EEI_{min}},$$

where EEI_{min} and EEI_{max} are laboratory limits or range in the sample.

2. Level of attention (Attention Index). The indicator shows how well the content holds visual attention. To measure attention, eye tracking records which elements the eye focuses on while watching a video clip: a face, a logo, a product, or a landscape. For example, if the majority of viewers focus on shots with people, this indicates the effectiveness of emotional storytelling and its positive perception.

The indicator is calculated using the formula for each area of interest (AOI):

$$AI_{AOI} = \frac{T_{AOI}}{\sum_{k=1}^K T_K},$$

where AI_{AOI} is the level of attention (eye tracking); T_{AOI} is the total time of gaze fixations in the selected area of interest; $\sum_{k=1}^K T_K$ – total fixation time for all zones of interest; K is the number of interest zones.

3. Authenticity Perception reflects the extent to which the viewer perceives the video as authentic and natural. A short survey can assess this indicator after viewing. A point scale is used in the survey, for example, from 1 to 5, where 1 indicates a negative perception of the video as fake and staged, and 5 indicates the most positive perception as trustworthy and credible. Videos with real producers, local sounds, and minimal production receive higher authenticity scores.

The formula determines the Authenticity Score (AS) indicator:

$$AS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \times s_i}{m} ; s_i \in [1; 5],$$

where s_i – evaluation of the video according to the i -th statement of the questionnaire; m is the number of statements.

4. The Trust Index (TI) shows whether the content evokes a feeling of honesty and trustworthiness of the brand. It is composed of both emotional and visual signals: open gestures by the characters, sincere smiles, natural lighting, and familiar landscapes.

The indicator TI is calculated according to the formula:

$$TI = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \times t_j}{n} ; t_j \in [1; 5],$$

where t_j is the video rating under the j -th trust criterion, and n is the number of criteria..

5. The level of memorability (Recall Rate) evaluates which elements of the video remain in the memory of the viewer after a long time. For this purpose, logo, location or main character recognition tests can be used.

The indicator is calculated according to the formula:

$$Recall = \frac{C}{Q} ,$$

where $Recall$ is the level of memorability; C is the number of correct answers in the recognition test; and Q is the total number of questions.

6. An indicator of Emotional Arousal that can be recorded through changes in heart rate or skin conductivity. High values indicate that the content evokes a strong emotional response.

The indicator is calculated using a formula that reflects the combination of the peak frequency and the average amplitude relative to the base level::

$$AI_{GSR} = \left(\frac{f}{f_0}\right) \times \left(\frac{A}{A_0}\right) ,$$

where AI_{GSR} is the level of physiological response (Arousal Index); f is peaks/min during viewing; f_0 is bare peaks/min at rest; A is the average amplitude of the skin-galvanic reaction; A_0 is the basic amplitude.

All these neuromarketing indicators determine which elements of the video influence the viewer's reaction and perception of content with terroir. For example, calm scenes with natural colors evoke trust and a sense of stability. Dynamic shots of harvest or craft work enhance interest and engagement. And the combination of sounds of nature, traditional music and local language creates the effect of the authenticity of the terroir. Using the selected indicators allows for an objective assessment of the effectiveness of video content about terroir, adaptation to the target audience, and increased trust in brands that represent the products of a specific region. For example, Ukrainian wineries filming short videos about their vineyards can use eye tracking to determine whether viewers notice a logo or the name of the region. Dairy cooperatives or farms can test the emotional impact of videos that show animals, a farming family, and rural nature. Tourism brands can analyze the trust index to understand whether videos with local residents generate more interest than commercials.

To generalize the evaluation of video content perception of terroir, it is advisable to use the integral indicator of emotional involvement (EEI_{pred}), a linear generalized metric for comparing videos. This indicator is calculated according to the formula::

$$EEI_{pred} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot AS + \beta_2 \cdot VIL + \beta_3 \times NC ,$$

where $AS \in [1; 5]$ – authenticity index; $VIL \in [0; 1]$ – level of visual immersion (share of fixations on key *AOIs*); $NC \in [1;5]$ – expert evaluation of the integrity of the narrative; $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ are given weighting factors.

The considered indicators enable quantifying audience reactions and identifying which elements of the content strengthen authenticity and trust in the brand.

Conclusions. Therefore, in modern conditions, the concept of terroir is gradually shifting from an agrarian concept to a marketing category of authenticity, with important theoretical and practical significance for modern branding. Terroir in video storytelling is a key factor in shaping a brand image, fostering consumer

emotional involvement, and increasing trust. The use of neuromarketing indicators provides an objective assessment of the audience's emotional and cognitive responses to content. It enables quantitative measurement of the impact of authentic video stories on brand perception.

The results demonstrate relationships among the authenticity of video content, emotional involvement, and consumer trust, which lay the foundation for successful advertising campaigns. The practical application of neuromarketing indicators in video marketing will enhance the effectiveness of communication strategies for brands that focus on the values of place, traditions, and culture. Further research should focus on developing integrated models to evaluate the emotional authenticity of content and on using artificial intelligence to analyze viewers' reactions in real time.

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